

How Cut Foliage Could Align with Agroforestry in Ireland

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A selection of Irish cut foliage

Integrating cut foliage production into agroforestry systems in Ireland offers farmers the opportunity to diversify income while improving environmental sustainability. Cut foliage, including decorative branches and leaves, is in high demand for floral arrangements, with established markets in the UK and the Netherlands. Ireland's mild, moist climate, particularly in the south, is well-suited for species like *Pittosporum* and *Prunus*. By incorporating these species into agroforestry, farmers can generate additional income while benefiting from the environmental advantages of tree-based systems.

Potentially, a major advantage of a cut foliage agroforestry system is resource efficiency, as foliage production can be integrated with livestock grazing, silvopasture, or agrisilviculture (alleyalley cropping), maximizing land use while improving ecosystem services. Successful implementation requires careful species selection, prioritizing hardy, fast-growing plants that regenerate quickly after harvesting. Proper site preparation is also essential, with well-drained, sheltered locations preferred. Effective weed control and soil conditioning would help establish strong plants that produce high-quality foliage. Effective management practices ensure sustainable production and long-term profitability. Regular pruning encourages strong regrowth, maintains plant health, and produces high-quality stems suited for market demands. Monitoring for pests and diseases is crucial, with sustainable integrated pest control (IPM) methods recommended to avoid chemical overuse. By integrating cut foliage into agroforestry, Irish farmers can enhance farm resilience, protect natural resources, and tap into profitable decorative plant markets.

However, cut foliage is not currently eligible under Ireland's agroforestry aid scheme.

References
DTeagasc. (2023). Cut Foliage Production in Ireland: An Overview of Practices and Market Potential. Available at: https://www.teagasc.ie/media/website/crops/horticulture/cut-foliage/1_20-Cut-Foliage-Production-.pdf

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